

Workshop Proposal for I-RIM 2024

Title: Bridging the reality gap: can we trust upper-limb exoskeletons in clinical practice?

Format: Half-day workshop:

- Invited talks / Round table
- Poster session and demos

Website: Check the programme details and updates on the dedicated website

(<https://sites.google.com/view/btrg-irim24>)

Organizers

Nicola SECCIANI, Chiara BROGI, Alberto TOPINI, Alessandro RIDOLFI	Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Florence	nicola.secciani@unifi.it chiara.brogi@unifi.it alberto.topini@unifi.it alessandro.ridolfi@unifi.it
Mihai DRAGUSANU, Danilo TROISI	Department of Information Engineering and Mathematics, University of Siena	mihai.dragusanu2@unisi.it daniilo.troisi@student.unisi.it
Matteo RUSSO	Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Rome Tor Vergata	matteo.russo@uniroma2.it

Scope and format

Medical exoskeletons—wearable robotic devices that augment or replace lost limb functionalities—have captured significant interest in the field of **Robotics for Medicine and Healthcare** in recent years. Their potential for improving function and dexterity in individuals with neuromotor conditions (like stroke or spinal cord injury) is undeniable. Research efforts have been particularly flourishing lately, presenting a diverse array of exoskeleton designs documented in the scientific literature and attracting large investments and major funding allocations. Through the **Tuscany Health Ecosystem (THE)** and the **Fit For Medical Robotics (FIT4MEDROB)** project alone, the PNRR (“Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza”) and PNC (“Piano Nazionale Complementare”) have budgeted a total of nearly €250 million on the topic for the three-year period 2023 - 2026.

However, **despite this surge in innovation, they have not yet achieved widespread adoption within clinical practice: the use of upper limb exoskeletons, in particular, appears to be quite lagging behind.** Several key challenges—such as technological limitations, cost, and integration into therapy—are impeding this transition. In fact, current exoskeletons often lack the dexterity and adaptability to completely mirror the intricate movements of the human body. Additionally, bulkiness and weight can hinder user comfort and long-term wearability. On the economical side, the cost of developing and manufacturing these devices is still significant, while reimbursement policies often lag behind technological advancements, making access to this technology difficult for patients. The sum of these factors causes the effective integration of upper-limb exoskeletons into established clinical practice to require further research and development.

Addressing these challenges is crucial to unlocking the full potential of upper-limb exoskeletons, and cannot be done without a multidisciplinary co-design that involves engineers, clinicians, stakeholders and end-users. **The purpose of this workshop is precisely to analyze from such different perspectives how close or far upper-limb exoskeletons are to clinical practice presently, and to discuss what possible steps can be taken to bridge the reality gap in the near future.**

The workshop will be organized as follows:

- Session 1 - Invited talks / Round table
- Session 2 - Coffee break, poster session and demos
- Session 3 - Awards and conclusions

Topics (topics of interest include, but are not limited to)

- Robotics for Medicine and Healthcare
- Rehabilitation and Assistive Robotics
- Wearable devices
- Advanced technologies in clinical environments
- Technology-assisted therapies
- Technology acceptance, comfort, and usability

Invited speakers / round table participants

- Sara Vannelli (University of Florence)
- Fortunato Frisina (Tor Vergata University Hospital)
- Valentina Azzolini (Pisa University Hospital)
- Stefano Doronzio (IRCCS Fondazione Don Carlo Gnocchi)
- Daniele Leonardis (SSSA Pisa)
- Monica Tiboni/Cinzia Amici (University of Brescia, to be confirmed)
- Federico Mugione (CARF Tamburino, to be confirmed)

Expected outcomes

Due to the novelties of the proposed theme, we will ask the speakers to exploit the discussion at the workshop to propose either a special issue in a journal or a position paper describing the perspective toward a broader adoption of technology in the clinical practice.

Expected audience

The workshop is organized within the framework of the two PNRR/PNC research projects “THE” and “FIT4MEDROB”. The workshop will provide the opportunity to present and discuss the project activities and perspectives to the conference participants and to contact other researchers, stakeholders and end-users potentially interested in contributing to them. Overall, we expect an attendance of:

- Researchers working on related projects (approx. 10)
- Participants to the poster session (approx. 10)
- Other interested robotics researchers (approx. 10)
- Clinicians and stakeholders (approx. 5)